

The background of the entire page is a photograph of a Spanish cityscape, likely Salamanca, featuring a prominent Gothic cathedral tower in the center and a domed building to the right. The scene is captured in warm, golden-hour lighting. The image is framed by yellow wavy borders at the top and bottom.

MODERN APPROACHES AND SOLUTIONS

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MODERN APPROACHES AND SOLUTIONS
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Репродуктивное развитие прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства о производственных отходах, а также его роль в системе обеспечения соблюдения законодательства в данной сфере

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Для начала необходимо отметить, что понятие «репродуктивное развитие», для более ясного его понимания, можно заменить более общеупотребляемыми словами, как национальное устойчивое развитие или интенсивное внедрение. Согласно Чижикю А.С., автору научной работы «Направления устойчивого развития национальной экономики», данное понятие представляет собой положительный устойчивый процесс эволюции, который удовлетворяет текущие потребности населения и не компрометирует возможность будущих поколений удовлетворить собственные потребности, сохраняя при этом окружающую среду .

Согласно же Левиной Е.И., автору работы «Понятие устойчивое развитие. Основные положения концепции», понятие данному термину выглядит следующим образом: это развитие, при котором удовлетворение потребностей настоящего времени не подрывает способность будущих поколений удовлетворять свои собственные потребности .

Опираясь на вышеуказанные определения, а также изучение других научных работ теоретиков и практиков, автор данной работы приходит к

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выводу о том, что термин «национальное репродуктивное развитие» представляет собой стратегическую концепцию, направленную на устойчивое развитие нации путем обеспечения гармоничного взаимодействия между экономическим, социальным и экологическим измерениями, то есть подразумевает создание условий для удовлетворения текущих потребностей населения, не оказывая при этом негативного влияния на способность будущих поколений удовлетворять свои собственные потребности. Необходимо добавить, что основные принципы национального репродуктивного развития включают в себя экономическую эффективность, социальную справедливость и экологическую устойчивость. Обосновывается же это тем, что экономическая эффективность обеспечивает рост производства и богатства нации, социальная справедливость гарантирует равный доступ к ресурсам и возможностям для всех членов общества, а экологическая устойчивость направлена на сохранение природных ресурсов и охрану окружающей среды.

Ввиду того, что мы рассматриваем данное понятие в контексте развития прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства о производственных отходах, можно сделать вывод, что оно подразумевает непрерывное и сознательное внедрение мер и механизмов, направленных на обеспечение соблюдения нормативных требований в области обращения с производственными отходами, то есть подчеркивает не только важность экономического и социального благосостояния, но и обеспечение экологической устойчивости национальной экономики, так как развитие прокурорского надзора обеспечивает эффективное применение законодательства о производственных отходах, контролируя соблюдение предприятиями и организациями требований по обращению с отходами и предотвращая их негативное воздействие на окружающую среду.

Разобравшись с определением данного понятия, стоит перейти к разбору самого национального репродуктивного развития прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства о производственных отходах. Стоит начать с того, что основными нормативно-правовыми актами, регулирующие прокурорский надзор в сфере обращения с производственными отходами в Узбекистане, являются Закон Республики Узбекистан «О прокуратуре» и Закон Республики Узбекистан «Об охране природы», которые устанавливают основные принципы и правила в области экологического законодательства, включая требования к обращению с отходами, а также ответственность за их ненадлежащее управление. Учитывая же тот факт, что в настоящее время количество новых нормативно-правовых актов, принятых нормотворческими органами, имеет тенденцию увеличиваться, а качество и обхват старых, тенденцию улучшаться, можно утверждать, что сознание как народа, так и правительства, движется в правильном направлении, а именно в направлении исправления нынешней экологической ситуации. Подтверждением данных слов может выступить принятие таких дополнительных нормативно-правовых актов как, например, Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по охране окружающей среды и организации деятельности государственных органов в сфере экологического контроля», принятое ранее Постановление Президента Республики Узбекистан «О мерах по кардинальному совершенствованию и развитию системы обращения с отходами на 2017 — 2021 годы», Постановление Кабинета Министров Республики Узбекистан «Об утверждении нормативно-правовых актов в области обращения с отходами», которые направлены на конкретизацию положений основного законодательства и установление конкретных требований к деятельности предприятий в области обращения с отходами.

Стоит добавить, что в нашей стране принимаются и уже приняты меры

по улучшению открытости таких данных, как количество выброшенных и производимых отходов, например, через соответствующие государственные органы, как Агентство статистики при Президенте Республики Узбекистан, что может являться дополнительным подтверждением осознанного движения государства и населения в борьбе с возникшей проблемой. Введение и наличие статистических данных играет немаловажную роль в борьбе с ними, так как статистика по производственным отходам важна для оценки состояния экологической ситуации и эффективности мер, предпринимаемых государственными органами, по ее улучшению, например, данные о количестве производственных отходов, образующихся на предприятиях различных отраслей экономики, могут свидетельствовать о том, насколько успешно внедряются технологии очистки и утилизации отходов, в то время, как анализ статистики позволяет выявлять тенденции в изменении объемов отходов и принимать меры по их сокращению. Также статистика может выявить регионы с наибольшей концентрацией загрязнений, что позволит сосредоточить усилия на их снижении. Все вышперечисленное является не только сподвижником возникновения прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства с сфере производственных отходов, но и компаньоном, так как указывает на то, в каких регионах и среди каких хозяйствующих субъектов надо ужесточить или ослабить данный вид надзора.

Хотелось бы добавить тот факт, что изучение статистики выступает лишь основой, в ходе которого могут быть выявлены правонарушения в сфере экологии, а основные полномочия органов прокуратуры, согласно статье 22 Закона Республики Узбекистан «О прокуратуре», включают в себя беспрепятственное вхождение на территорию и в помещения министерств, ведомств, предприятий, учреждений, организаций, воинских частей, наличие доступа к документам и материалам, проведение проверок, права требования

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для проверки решения, распоряжения, приказов и иных документов, сведений о состоянии законности и мерах по ее обеспечению, право требования от руководителей и других должностных лиц государственных органов, воинских частей, воинских формирований министерств и ведомств проведения проверок, ревизий деятельности подведомственных предприятий, учреждений, организаций, выделение специалистов для проведения ведомственных и вневедомственных проверок, право требования от должностных лиц и граждан устных или письменных объяснений относительно нарушения закона, что подтверждает как наличие больших полномочий органов прокуратуры в данной сфере, так и их пределов. Основным ограничением прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства о производственных отходах выступает также статья 21 ранее упомянутого Закона Республики Узбекистан «О прокуратуре», в которой сказано о том, что данный вид надзора может быть осуществлен лишь на основании заявлений и других сообщений о нарушениях законов, что говорит об ограниченности оснований для осуществления надзора. Ввиду этого, по мнению автора данной диссертационной работы, изучивший определенные научные статьи теоретиков и практиков, вышеупомянутая статья может быть дополнена следующими основаниями: на основе материалов уголовных, административных и гражданских дел. Учитывая же важность введения и анализа статистических данных, можно добавить в список оснований также результаты анализа достоверной статистики государственных органов, о чем и говорит Карпов Н.Н., в своей книге «Теоретические вопросы деятельности прокуратуры по надзору за исполнением законов и законностью правовых актов», который также отмечает о том, что некие ограничения в законе «не означают, что прокурор должен сидеть на рабочем месте сложа руки и ждать поступления так

называемых сигналов» .

Другой статьей, указывающей на наличие определенных пределов данного вида надзора, выступает статья 20 ранее упомянутого закона, которая описывает предмет данного надзора и в которой отсутствует упоминание о полномочиях органов прокуратуры осуществлять надзор за исполнением законов не должностными лицами, то есть гражданами, которые также могут выступать субъектами, например, правонарушений в сфере производственных отходов. Примером такого правонарушения является часть 4 статьи 65 Кодекса Республики Узбекистан об Административной Ответственности, в которой предусмотрена ответственность за порчу сельскохозяйственных и других земель, загрязнение их производственными и иными отходами, химическими и радиоактивными веществами и сточными водами, субъектом которого могут выступать обычные граждане, о чем прямо сказано в санкционной части данной статьи. По мнению автора данной работы, это является неким упущением нормотворческих органов, так как ограничивает проведение прокурорского надзора за гражданами-правонарушителями в данной сфере.

Подводя итог данной части, можно сказать, что национальное репродуктивное развитие прокурорского надзора над исполнением законодательства о производственных отходах демонстрирует постепенный рост, однако органам прокуратуры до сих пор не предоставлены все необходимые полномочия для полного и эффективного старта и осуществления данного вида надзора, предполагающий собой, что, несмотря на прогресс, существуют препятствия для полноценного контроля за соблюдением законодательства об управлении производственными отходами.

Изучив вопросы национального репродуктивного развития

прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства о производственных отходах, а также его пределов, стоит перейти к изучению роли прокурорского надзора в обеспечении соблюдения законодательства о производственных отходах.

Как показывает изученная литература и практика, прокуратура является ключевым институтом, обладающим правом на осуществление надзора за соблюдением законности в области обращения с производственными отходами, роль которой заключается в осуществлении систематического контроля, анализе и реагировании на возможные нарушения законодательства, направленных на обеспечение экологической безопасности и соблюдение прав граждан. Одним из главных аспектов, подчеркиваемых в научной литературе, является необходимость противодействия безнаказанности и произволу в сфере обращения с производственными отходами. Отсутствие строгого контроля и надзора может способствовать формированию негативной практики, при которой предприятия могут игнорировать экологические стандарты и принимать меры, которые наносят ущерб окружающей среде и здоровью людей, что отмечается и Гаджиевым Н.Г., Коноваленко С.А., авторами научной статьи «Анализ и статистическая оценка современного состояния экологической преступности, пути повышения эффективности их выявления», которые в своей статье указывают, что без ужесточения уголовной политики в сфере экологии, невозможно будет добиться результата перехода к курсе «зеленой экономики» .

Прокурорский надзор же предполагает активное вмешательство в случае выявления нарушений законодательства о производственных отходах, что в свою очередь способствует поддержанию порядка, обеспечению исполнения законов и защите интересов не только нынешнего поколения, но и будущего, так как проблема экологии не касается определенных лиц, а несет в себе более

обширный характер. Важно отметить, что прокурорский надзор в данной сфере не ограничивается только выявлением нарушений, но и предполагает принятие мер по их устранению и наказанию виновных лиц, что обеспечивает эффективное функционирование системы контроля и превентивные меры в отношении будущих правонарушений, что, в теории, снижает их количество.

Таким образом, роль прокуратуры в области обращения с производственными отходами не только важна, но и необходима для предотвращения нарушений и обеспечения экологической безопасности. Отсутствие контроля может привести к серьезным последствиям для окружающей среды и здоровья людей, поэтому эффективная деятельность прокуратуры в данной сфере является неотъемлемой частью общественного управления и охраны здоровья населения, что также подтверждается словами Ерохова В.В., автора работы «К вопросу о повышении эффективности прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства об обращении с отходами производства и потребления», в которой он отмечал, что увеличение эффективности надзора прокуратуры за соблюдением законодательства о промышленных отходах не только способствует закреплению правопорядка в этой области, но также является одним из методов повышения эффективности работы государственных и других контролирующих органов.

Говоря о серьезных последствиях отсутствия контроля, хотелось бы привести несколько примеров из жизнедеятельности зарубежных стран, в которой видны последствия упущения контроля за данной сферой.

Примером недавних новостей о последствиях игнорирования законодательства о производственных отходах является ситуация в США, где в результате недостаточного контроля за выбросами и обращением с промышленными отходами произошли серьезные экологические катастрофы. Например, в штате Калифорния произошел разлив нефти в результате

нарушения технических правил на нефтепроводе, что привело к серьезному загрязнению природных водоемов и ущерб для местной фауны и флоры .

Еще одним примером является ситуация в Европе, где ряд предприятий, не соблюдая законодательство о производственных отходах, выбрасывали свои отходы в водоемы или на землю. Это произошло в Италии, в муниципалитете Кальви Ризорта к северу от Неаполя, где было обнаружено крупнейшее в Европе нелегальное захоронение токсичных отходов. Химикаты здесь прятала мафия, оплачиваемая местными предприятиями, которые не хотели заниматься дорогостоящим процессом утилизации . В результате этого произошло загрязнение атмосферного воздуха и почв, а также возникла угроза здоровью местного населения.

Эти примеры являются лишь результатом лишь поверхностного изучения проблемы, связанной с нарушениями законодательства о производственных отходах. Они демонстрируют, что отсутствие строгого контроля и недостаточная ответственность предприятий и организаций может привести к серьезным экологическим последствиям, которые затрагивают не только местные сообщества, но и имеют глобальное значение для всей планеты.

Далее, предоставив примеры результатов оплошности надзора, стоит упомянуть и некоторые примеры улучшения ситуации, произошедшей после вмешательства в них органов прокуратуры. В качестве примера можем предоставить статистику США, в которой видно, что вмешательство прокурорского надзора и ужесточение наказаний за нарушения экологических законов привело к сокращению числа случаев нелегальной вырубке лесов, разливов опасных веществ в водоемы и других экологических преступлений, что можно подтвердить при помощи отчета агентства федерального правительства США «Environmental Protection Agency» , изучение которой

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дало возможность сделать вывод о том, что за последние годы отмечается снижение числа нарушений законодательства в области охраны окружающей среды и увеличение количества успешных расследований и привлечений к ответственности за экологические преступления.

**MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE BUDGET-FISCAL POLICY OF
UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: This article presents an analysis of the main priorities of the budget and tax policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023, in which complex economic processes in the world market, the tension in the geopolitical situation in the world and its impact on the economy of Uzbekistan, changes in the budget and tax policy of Uzbekistan, state budget revenues and expenses are analyzed.

Key words: budget, tax, tax policy, economic growth, budget revenues, budget expenditures, deficit.

The Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2022, the leader of our country spoke about the socio-economic development of our country. speaking about the priority directions of development , " You are all aware of the sharp processes taking place in the world today . Despite the complex geopolitical situation in the world, the shortage of energy resources is increasing , the demand for energy is increasing , and financial resources are becoming more expensive .

In such a situation, no matter how difficult it may be , we will continue economic reforms, fully mobilize domestic capabilities, and further strengthen the private sector. For this, first of all, we will speed up the reforms to further improve the business environment .

, disruptions in the global supply chain, the tension in the geopolitical situation in the world, the inflationary pressures and economic depressions caused by the conflicts between the states cannot be saved on a global scale . Such external threats, in turn, have a negative impact on the national economy , causing inflation to be higher than expected , and negatively impacting economic activity .

According to the forecasts of the World Bank, in 2022, the world economy is expected to grow by 2.9%, the economy of developed countries is expected to grow by 2.6%, and the economy of developing countries is expected to grow by 3.4 % .

Despite the uncertainty in the world market and the difficult situation in our main foreign trade partners, as a result of the economic reforms implemented in previous years, economic growth in 2023 is forecast to be around 5 percent . This economic growth rate is expected to increase the industry by 6 % , the service sector by 14 % , the construction sector by 6 % , and the agriculture sector by 3.5 % . . The export volume of our country is expected to increase by 23 billion 241 million dollars or 22.8% .

Also, in 2023, consolidated budget revenues in our country are planned to be

311 trillion soms , and expenditures are planned to be 343 trillion soms , the consolidated budget is 32 trillion 528 billion soms or 3 % compared to the gross domestic product . a shortage of medicine was determined.[1]

, the tax reforms implemented during the previous years gave a positive result. In particular, starting from 2018, we can see that the amount of revenues to the budget continues to grow as a result of the tax reforms initiated by the President , the reduction of tax types , the reduction of tax rates and the expansion of the tax base . [2]

At the same time , the procedure for taxing incomes in the form of payment for labor will be fundamentally improved , and the 8 percent tax on the income of individuals As a result of the cancellation of the contribution and the establishment of a single rate of 4- point income tax with a tax rate of up to 22.5% to 12%, the total revenues have doubled and increased from 26 trillion 500 billion soums to almost 52 trillion 500 billion soums . At the same time, the number of workers paying income **tax in 2018** is more than 5 million 300 thousand people from 3 million 900 thousand people, and it is not expected to increase further in the following years .

In general, as a result of the reforms carried out in recent years, the budget revenues increased sharply, in 2018, the state budget revenues amounted to 82 trillion 800 billion soums, and in 2022, they amounted to 205 trillion soums. At the same time, it is possible to achieve a year-by-year decrease in budget revenues due to gold prices .

The revenues of the 2023 budget are planned based on the main macroeconomic indicators, the expected prices of raw materials on the world market, changes in the tax policy, and the improvement of the tax and customs administration .

In the tax policy set for 2023, the main tax rates were kept at the base rate of profit tax at 15 percent, income tax from individuals at 12 percent, and property tax at 1.5 percent .

Along with this, a number of important changes were made in determining the tax policy of 2023 in order to increase investment attractiveness in the republic .

Firstly, the VAT rate was reduced from the current 15% to 12% for the purpose of reducing and unifying tax rates and creating additional opportunities to further improve the business environment . This is a historically important change in the tax policy of our country. As a result of the reduction of the tax rate to 3 percent, 13 trillion soums of working capital are at the disposal of entrepreneurs. increase is planned, which will lead to the optimization of the tax burden on enterprises.[3]At the same time, it is predicted that in 2023, the income from this tax will be 16 trillion soums more than in 2022.[4]

Secondly, to ensure the stability of local budget revenues, strictly defined tax rates and bases are supposed to be indexed within the framework of inflation or by 10 percent. In this case, it is planned to implement the indexation of excise tax rates

from February 1, 2023.

Thirdly, the work of gradually canceling tax benefits is still ongoing. In particular, from April 1, 2023, benefits from the value added tax on a number of services provided from budget funds will not be canceled, and as a result, an additional tax revenue of 109 billion soums is expected for the budget .

At the same time, the expiration of the tax and customs benefits[5] granted by other regulatory and legal documents in 2023 was also taken into account in the budget revenues.

Fourthly, about 1 percent of the gross domestic product or 9 trillion 200 billion soums is provided in the budget revenues for the purpose of improving the tax and customs administration.

State budget expenditures for 2023 will amount to 257 trillion 734 billion soums, which will provide stimulation of economic growth by increasing expenditures aimed at the development of certain sectors . In this:

50 percent of expenses or 130 trillion soums will be directed to the social sector. Social sector expenses include mainly:

58 trillion 372 billion soums or 23% of the total expenses of the state budget and 16% more than the 2022 implementation are planned for the education sector .

7 trillion 585 billion soums are planned for the implementation of 18 state programs in the field of education . Including:

- allocation of subsidies in the amount of 2 trillion 259 billion soums from the State budget to non-state preschool educational institutions ;

- 920 billion soums for costs related to updating textbooks in general secondary education institutions;

- soums for the purpose of increasing the quotas for admission to higher education institutions on the basis of a state grant ;

- from budget funds to education loans in order to create favorable conditions and equal opportunities for every student studying on a fee-contract basis ;

- 284 billion soums are planned for building student residences and allocating subsidies for each student living in them .

28 trillion 426 billion soums are planned for health care . From this, 1 trillion 500 billion soums are planned for the implementation of 22 state programs related to this field . Including:

- 31 billion soums for the costs of additional provision of necessary drugs and medical equipment to ensure the health of mothers and children, women of reproductive age;

- 138 billion soums for expenses related to improvement of oncology care and further development of oncology services ;

In addition , 33 trillion 67 billion soums are planned for social protection and social security . Including:

- 15 trillion soums to cover the negative difference between the income and

expenses of the pension fund outside the budget ;

- 18 trillion 67 billion soums are planned for financial support of low - income families and people in need of social protection .

In 2023 , 10 trillion 530 billion soums are planned to pay social benefits to 1.9 million families, 20 percent of all families in our republic .

966 billion soums are planned for the payment of maternity benefits for working women from budget funds, of which 300 billion soums are planned for women working in the private sector.

In the draft budget for the next year , a total of 30 trillion soums for financing infrastructure development programs, including:

- 15 trillion 520 billion soums for the centralized investment program;
- 3 trillion 500 billion soums for socio-economic development of regions and sectors ;

- 11 trillion 25 billion soums are planned for infrastructure improvement measures. Of this, 6 trillion soums are being allocated for the initiative budget project, as well as 30% of additional sources of local budgets and a total of 8 trillion soums in 2023, taking into account the funds provided for internal roads in local budgets.[6]

At the same time, special attention is paid to the support of women and young people in the draft budget , 6 trillion 569 billion soums are envisaged. In 2022, 4 trillion 308 billion soums were allocated in this direction.

In 2023, economic expenses will amount to 36 trillion 680 billion soums, of which 10 trillion 600 billion soums are planned for agriculture and water management. [7]

Based on this, the deficit of the State budget and target funds for the next year was set at 24 trillion 215 billion soums or 2.3 percent of GDP. This, in turn, will lead to a certain reduction of the tax burden in our country, and its impact on the activities of business entities will decrease.[8]

In general, the State budget of 2023 was formed based on the interests of the people and the priorities set by the head of our country, aimed at glorifying "Human dignity" and improving people's lives, as well as improving the standard of living of the population: including:

- creation of favorable business conditions for entrepreneurs;
- development of the social sphere and strengthening of social protection;
- supporting youth and women;
- h regions, especially solving the urgent problems of the neighborhoods, rational use of water and land resources, environmental protection have been identified as priorities.

Quality and full performance of the works to be carried out in these directions, rational use of allocated budget funds and ensuring their effectiveness should be the main task of the state and citizens .

REFERENCES

1. Sharipovich B. A., Shukhratovich T. S. (2022). Ustoychivyy ekonomicheski rost i effektivnaya nalogovaya politika. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(8), 14.
2. Shukhratovich, T. S. (2021). Tax burden and macroeconomic stability and investment performance and environment. *epra international journal of multidisciplinary research (ijmr)*, 7(5), 1-1.
3. Turaev, Sh. (2022). Problems of optimization of the current situation in enterprises . *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 10(3), 378-385.
4. Turaev, SS (2021). Methodology for calculation of the tax burden on legal entities and directions of improvement. *theoretical and applied sciences*, (5), 235-238.
5. S. Turaev, "Improving the procedure for calculating the tax burden by digital technologies", 2021 International Conference on Informatics and Communication Technologies (ICISCT), Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2021, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICISCT52966.2021.9670039

MAIN ISSUES OF FINANCING SOCIAL EXPENDITURES

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Annotation. Budgets vary depending on the direction of spending. If the costs of the economy and management are high, this means radical changes in the country's macroeconomic policy. In fact, the state budget must be socialized in essence; for this, domestic investments must be stimulated, and due to this, state costs in the economy must be reduced and its socialization increased. This process is the socialization of the budget process of Uzbekistan and has its own characteristics. This dissertation highlights the main directions of the socialized budget and issues of further improvement of the process in this direction.

Keywords. State budget, social expenditures, socialized budget, education expenditures, expenses, financing, social sector, healthcare. general education, school, cost estimates, first-level budget allocators, second-level budget allocators.

Every year in Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, in accordance with the Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, develops the State Budget, which is a document that defines the main directions of the country's socio-economic development for the future period. Uzbekistan. It includes macroeconomic indicators for the medium term, forecasts of income and expenditure of the consolidated budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its deficit, information on sources of financing the deficit, the main directions of fiscal policy, and macroeconomic indicators. budget risks and analysis of public debt reforms planned to develop and improve public financial management, including increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of budget expenditures, ensuring budget openness, harmonizing expenditures with sustainable development goals, reforms aimed at the transition to "green" development. economics and budgeting, as well as improving internal control and internal audit in the public sector includes measures that need to be implemented to

To achieve macroeconomic and fiscal stability in the long term, the deficit needs to be reduced to an average of 3 percent over the medium term. To ensure that it does not exceed, it will be necessary to gradually reduce the size of the deficit by optimizing budget funds, expanding the revenue base, and eliminating ineffective tax breaks and preferences. Due to the fact that the upper limit of the budget deficit in 2024 is set at 4 percent, the amount of external debt raised to finance investment projects will be maintained, and the limited amount of external debt to be raised will

be US\$5.0 billion. US dollars , of which 2.5 billion US dollars State budget support, including financing of the budget deficit, the rest is aimed at financing investment projects .

At the same time, in order to diversify the public debt portfolio and reduce currency risks, the limited net volume of government securities that will be issued on behalf of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024 is set at 25 trillion soums (in 2023 - 17 trillion soums). . In order to ensure the growth of the economy of Uzbekistan within the forecast indicators, a fiscal policy that is flexible to external and internal influences is being implemented, aimed at ensuring macroeconomic and budgetary stability. In this case, it will be necessary to maintain public debt at a safe level for macroeconomic stability, not to increase the consolidated budget deficit compared to the approved forecast, to improve the system for assessing macro-fiscal risks, and to ensure that the consolidated budget is fully covered. , ensuring openness at all stages of the budget process and other similar promising areas.

Despite the difficult situation observed in the global economy over the past 4 years, as a result of reforms aimed at liberalizing the economy, in the country's development strategies and the implementation of programs aimed at developing industries, industries and regions, stable rates of economic growth in 2023 are ensured 5. 8 percent. Financing the economy and demand factors (demand coefficient) at the end of the current year, consolidated budget expenditures increased by 18.4 percent compared to the corresponding period last year , amounting to 380.9 trillion soums , which served as a stimulating factor for economic growth.

Table 1.

Wages and equivalent payments, *billion soums*

	202 3 years	202 forecast for 4 years	Difference	
			in total	in percentages
I. From the state budget	1 30 633	1 5 7 569	+2 6 936	+ 2 0 , 6
Share of the state budget in total expenditures, percentage	46 , 3	50 , 4	-	-
1. Wages and social tax	1 08 152	13 3 355	+2 5 203	+2 2 , 8
2 . Scholarships	1,597	1,958	+361	+22.6
3 . Social benefits	16 479	17,593	+ 1 114	+ 6.8
II. From the pension fund	5 3 8 53	63 137	9 284	+1 7.2
GENERAL	18 4 486	22 0 707	3 6 221	+ 19.6

Source: compiled by the author based on information from the Ministry of Finance and Economy.

From Table 1 it can be seen that in order to improve the standard of living of the population and ensure the growth of real incomes of citizens, wages and pensions are increasing every year. The socialization of the state budget is evidenced by the increase in wages in 2024 compared to 2023 by 22.6 percent or 361 trillion soums. If wages increase, this will affect the purchasing power of the population, since measures associated with reducing inflation to single digits will increase the purchasing power of the population as a result of such wage increases.

Another indicator characterizing the socialization of the state budget is the increase in the volume of funds allocated to finance educational loans. In 2021-2023, 3.3 trillion soums of resource funds were allocated for educational loans to a total of 315 thousand students , of which 219 thousand are women. Additionally, in 2024, funds are planned to provide educational loans to 180 thousand students, and the number of students covered by this program is expected to reach 500 thousand . 2.2 trillion soums are planned for these purposes in 2024 , of which 1.8 trillion soums will be used to finance education loans and 400 billion soums to cover the percentage of loans allocated to women.

Table 2.

Main indicators of secondary general education organizations

	20 20 years	2021	2022	2023	202 4 years
Total number of organizations, units.	10 193	10,292	10,507	10 520	10,620
secondary schools	9,920	9,924	9,959	9,972	10,072
boarding schools	227	231	227	227	227
orphanages	117	121	127	127	127
Presidential schools	-	4	14	14	14
creativity and specialized schools	-	12	180	180	180
students (thousands)	5995	6,280.2	6,405.9	6,534.0	6 666 , 9
current expenses (billion soums)	22,365.4	27,247.7	33,137.7	38,279.1	4 2 894.0
of which: per student (million soums)	3.7	4.3	5, 2	5, 8	6 , 4
Capital expenditures	3,365.0	3,374.0	3 029 , 2	2 760.2	4 100.0

Source: compiled by the author based on information from the Ministry of Finance and Economy.

In 2024, it is planned to allocate 13.5 trillion soums from the state budget to

finance preschool education organizations, which is 14.0 percent more than planned in 2023. At the same time, the bulk of expenses, that is, 51 percent, is allocated to wages and social tax expenses. It is planned to spend 42.9 trillion soums , or 12.1% more than the planned execution in 2023, to allocate 13.7% of the total expenditures of the State budget. At the same time, the main part of expenses, that is, 88 percent, falls on wages and social tax expenses.

In our opinion, in addition to the above, in order to increase the sociality of the State budget, it is advisable to pay special attention to the following:

It is necessary to improve the current criteria for determining the status of a low-income family. According to a survey conducted jointly with the World Bank, 14 percent of households in our country are classified as low-income. 23 percent of families receive social payments through the Unified Register of Social Protection. It is necessary to reach really needy families with the system of social benefits by improving the current criteria for payment of benefits;

From 2024, it is advisable to transfer child benefits and material assistance to low-income families from funding from the relevant local budgets to funding from the republican budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

To fully finance activities in the field of social protection, we believe that it is necessary to generate expenses of the National Social Protection Agency in the amount of 3.3 trillion soums;

In 2024, 1.5 trillion soums of subsidies should be paid from the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan to cover part of the down payment and interest on mortgage loans to citizens with low incomes and in need of improved housing conditions. Effective use of available financial resources in higher education institutions.

List of used literature:

1. Budget Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2024.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the State Budget for 2024. December 2023.
3. Budget strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2023-2026. Tashkent, 2023.
4. Dostmuhammad H.U. Ways to organize effective financing of public education: i.f.s. ...abstract. – T.: DJQA, 2012. – 24 p.
5. Norkabilov N.N. The role of marketing in extra-budgetary financing of the education and training system // Journal “Modern Education”.
6. Salomova B.V. Development of the education system as a factor in the development of the state (on the example of South Korea and Japan) // Journal of

MODERN APPROACHES AND SOLUTIONS

Spanish International Open Conference 2024

<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

Modern Education. – T.: 2017. – No. 9..33-41-B.

7. Sherov A.Yu. Analysis of factors determining the effectiveness of budget policy//Scientific electronic journal “Economics and Innovative Technologies”. No. 3, May-June 2019.

**THE CULTURE OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS IN STUDENTS
DEVELOPMENT NOW DAILY DOLLARITY**

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Annotation: the article is about the current relevance and importance of the development of the culture of interpersonal relations in students, and more attention is paid to the importance of the formation of a culture of interpersonal relations between the student body oath say strengthening the personality of the greatest reforms until their implementation in our country, developing correct adequate decision-making in

Keywords: communication, culture of communication, attitude interpersonal relationships complex relationships culture of attitude decision decree.

Prosperous life – perfect from upbringing starts. It is known that young generation upbringing has always been important and relevant. But we In the 21st century, this issue has truly become a matter of life and death is going "Education how much perfect if people that's all happy lives" that sages who did not say it for nothing. Education should be perfect in the current volatile times "It is absolutely impossible to allow a gap to appear in this matter." dear President Shaukat Mirziyoyev 1 .

Therefore, the consistent reforms carried out in our country, Uzbekistan Republic President Shaukat Mirziyoyev social and spiritual and educational to areas about young people in education new 7 important initiative, science, technique and rapid

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development of technologies, higher education institutions of foreign countries opening of branches and faculties, improvement of regulatory and legal support and material and technical conditions to improve directed country prospect for to educate young people who are able to take responsibility, enterprising, ambitious with one in line pedagogy higher education institutions future of teachers correcting their initiatives, eliminating conflict processes in them consistent with the educational system regarding the introduction and development of new literature changes is being entered. Uzbekistan Republic President 2017 year April 20 PQ-2909 - No. "On measures for further development of the higher education system" decision, 2017 year July 5 No. PF-5106 "To the youth about state policy efficiency Decree on increasing and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 PF- No. 5847 "Development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 Decree on approval of the concept of developed countries of the world study of educational experiences, local conditions, economic and intellectual resources taking into account the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society the fact that it is being increased ensures the achievement of new achievements.

1. Uzbekistan Republic President Shaukat Mirziyoyev Uzbekistan young people of the union IV his speech at the congress, 2017.

also this to the activity about another regulatory and legal in the documents defined tasks in the implementation of this tutorial will serve to a certain extent. Independence years the roof in a sense Uzbekistan Republic socio-economic and

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cultural development defining the perspective, taking a worthy place among the countries of the world community is going on with the implementation of large-scale work on the path of aspiration. Uzbekistan Republic President Shaukat Mirziyoyev as noted: "High education system modern methods using efficient management, in the field material and technical base strengthen, educational method things improvement according to serious measures we need to see. Real economic sectors considered personnel customers determining the strategy for the development of the higher education system based on the needs, state education standards and qualification requirements again work exit, of students it is necessary to effectively organize qualification practice" 1 . This, in turn, is higher education intellectually, morally, spiritually strong, mature qualified staff of teachers to be requirement is enough.

Reform of the national education system, content of education, training of pedagogues and their qualification increase programs improvement and specialists by of textbooks new generation in creating is used.

Today, it is important to create a democratic model of education from issues is one. education, especially, education process democratic of the model initial element student of the person individual activity showing manifestation will be People between relationships according to problems psychological advice transfer in practice too much occurs and customer they This is when he complains about other problems of a personal nature, even if he doesn't talk about it directly in fact in it interpersonal relationships according to his problem that there is no does not mean In life while a lot cases of this the opposite to be output: if the client interpersonal relationships according to there is status if concerned so in case each always in it own it will be possible to determine the problem of personal content related to the character. In addition, the practical solutions to these two problems are similar in many respects is similar. Nevertheless, these problems should be considered

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separately because they are always somewhat different than a personal content problem solution will be done. That's it of a person another people with relationships manage the way with will be resolved. In contrast, a person always solves his personal problems individually and another people with directly contact without doing too solution reach possible

From this except personal and interpersonal content problems solution reach in methods big difference there is. if personal problems usually of a person internal interpersonal problems, if it is related to the need to fundamentally change their world a person's behavior is mainly related to the need to change the external forms. Psychological problems related to a person's interactions with others can be different in terms of features. They are personal with the people around them and practical mutual relations with depends being to him near and much long was for example, it applies to relations with relatives and strangers possible This problem obvious expressed young difference too have will be.

For example, of the client peers or another generation, much young yes from himself much can occur in interactions with older people. Interpersonal relationships problems different sexual to people too concerned to be possible

Saying passed of problems a lot dimensionality people between mutual of relationships complexity shows. This of problems most of them this on the ground we separately discussion if we do both however this problems in life to each other dependence and the majority cases complex solution to be done necessity from memory not to issue need For example, common difficulties arise in interpersonal relationships there are some common reasons for its occurrence. However, human relations are different types special was private, to himself special difficulties reasons too there is.

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Interpersonal culture in students is the teacher's students with the psychological that is most convenient for him in class and extracurricular activities environment to the body causing positive spiritual the climate to create for chance giver professional is a relationship.

Teacher's students with mutually near communication main plan:

- negative circumstances to the body bringer all to processes I'm done to give
- in students independent thought conduct skills harvest to do;
- students to activity, free to think own opinions without fear statement by doing to him to rely on to teach;
- development of hidden abilities of students;
- lesson and from class except in processes joy and happiness get in the mood to do

Education receiver education - educational activity students with together organize is enough. In this of the class active students and informal leaders with mutually of communication fair to be important important has: students education different elements conscious to engage in independent performance, in which students are organized and executed roles to perform chance by creating to give must

Properly organized communication of the learner is the realization of the identity of the student function improves. In this education of the recipient task communication based on to help students to realize that they are "I", to express their opinion boldly and freely as a person to speak in the team own place to know self assessment to teach need

In students interpersonal relationship culture editorial communication structure in terms of is a unique example of student creativity. Pedagogical scientists of the learner students with communication many descriptions scientific in his works statement if they do communication, first education of the recipient personal psychological feature as manifestation will be

Students with corrective and developmental affairs

Education education in institutions educational of work the most important of duties one is the formation and development of the student body. It's not just this or that education applies not only to the educational institution, but also to a specific educational group - a class. Because where which in the team interpersonal relationships good organize done if there is, this team is the basis for successfully fulfilling the social tasks in front of it will be created. It is also good to introduce self-management in such a team effects to give possible Interpersonal relationships learning methods one The sociometer is a hypocrite method. The concept of sociometry by the American scientist J. Moreno offer done being in the group mutual relationships learning said the meaning means Sociometric method interpersonal relations in different groups, communities features of learning in psychology wide applied the most efficient is one of the tools. Sociometric analysis of the data held by the individual in the group instead of in the group interpersonal of relationships features, group stars, group the leader (recognized leader of the group) is isolated from the group remaining) member of in the group small groups (micro groups), their content, mutually relations and again series that's it such as information get enable gives

When solving problems in the system of interpersonal relations with students training training take to go efficient the result will give. In this on the shore from exercises use can:

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References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Critical analysis, strictly discipline and personal liability - every leader should have a daily rule of activity. Republic of Uzbekistan Dedicated to the results of 2016 and prospects of 2017 of the Cabinet of Ministers speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the meeting. // "Khalk sozi" newspaper, 2017, January 16, No 11.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. Great our future brave and Your Highness our people with together we will build – "Uzbekistan", 2017.
3. Uzbekistan Republic more development according to Actions strategy. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan documents collection, 2017, number 6, Article 70.
4. Mirziyoyev Sh. M. The rule of law is the development of human interests and people of well-being pledge – "Uzbekistan", 2017.
5. About the "Master-Apprentice" system at the Tashkent State University of Economics REGULATION. Spiritual and educational affairs and social protection Council 2005 January 21 meeting decision with approved (2004 year 25 August No. 87-02-1279 modem certificate).

Electronic education resources:

www.ziyonet.uz www.arxiv.uz www.tdpu.uz

Bolalarda tranzitor kasalliklar

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Annotatsiya: Bolaning tug'ruq stressiga, yangi yashash sharoitlariga moslashishini (adaptatsiya) aks ettiradigan reaksiyalar yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning chegaraviy (o'tish, tranzitor, neonatal fiziologik) holatlar deb ataladi. Bu holatlar, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning anatomik-fiziologik xususiyatlaridan farqli ravishda, tug'ruq vaqtida yoki tug'ilgandan so'ng paydo bo'ladi, so'ngra ma'lum vaqtdan keyin o'tib ketadi. Ushbu maqola bolalarda tranzitor kasalliklar haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tranzitor, neonatal fiziologik, bolalar, davolash.

Аннотация: Реакции, отражающие адаптацию ребенка к родовому стрессу и новым условиям жизни, называют пограничными (переходными, преходящими, неонатальными физиологическими) состояниями новорожденных. Эти состояния, в отличие от анатомо-физиологических особенностей новорожденных, появляются во время родов или после рождения, а затем исчезают через определенный промежуток времени. Эта статья о транзиторных заболеваниях у детей.

Ключевые слова: транзиторный, неонатальный физиологический, дети, лечение.

Abstract: Reactions that reflect the child's adaptation to childbirth stress and new living conditions are called borderline (transitional, transient, neonatal physiological) states of newborns. These conditions, unlike the anatomical and physiological characteristics of newborns, appear during childbirth or after birth, and then disappear after a certain period of time. This article is about transient diseases in children.

Key words: transient, neonatal physiological, children, treatment.

Tranzitor giperventilyatsiya

Bola tug'ilgandan so'nggi qichqirib yig'lashi uning dastlabki nafasidir.

Nafas olish tezligi bir daqiqada 30-60 marta, nafas olish xajmi esa 6-8 ml/kg tashkil etadi

Sog'lom chaqaloqlarda dastlabki 3 soat davomida gasps shaklida nafas (nafas olish chuqur, nafas chiqarish esa biroz qiyinlashgan) kuzatiladi, bu o'pkani ochilishiga va alveolani ichidagi fetal suyuqlikni evakuasiyasiga yordam beradi.

Moslashishi davrining dastlabki 2-3 kunlarida o'pkaning bir daqiqadagi havo almashinuvi katta yoshdagi bolalarga nisbatan 3 barobar ko'p bo'ladi.

Qon aylanishidagi tranzitor o'zgarishlar

Homilaning qon aylanishi yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarga nisbatan 3 ta asosiy xususiyat bilan ajralib turadi:

Plasentar qon aylanish doirasi borligi bilan;

Anatomik shuntlarni ochiqligi bilan (oval teshik, botallov tarmoqchasi, Aransiev tarmog'i);

O'pka orqali o'tadigan qon miqdori minimal (yurak qisqarishi xajmining 6-9% tashkil etadi).

Tranzitor politsitemiya

Bundan tashqari chaqaloq bolalarda politsitemiya (qizil qon tanachalarining odatdagidan ziyod bo'lishi) kuzatiladi. Bu holat gemoglobinining 180 - 220 g/l-dan ko'p bo'lishi va gematokritning 0,55-0,65 va undan ham yuqori, eritrotsitlar soni $6-8 \times 10^{12}/l$ bo'lishi bilan ta'riflanadi. Qon aylanishidagi bu tranzitor o'zgarishlar o'z-o'zidan yo'qolib, maxsus davolashni talab etmaydi.

Tranzitor disbakterioz

Ushbu holat 3 fazadan iborat.

Aseptik faza – ona ko'kragiga qo'ygunga qadar davom etadi

Infeksiyani ko'payish fazasi – bola hayotining 3-5 kunigacha kuzatiladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan mikroorganizmlarni ichakka tushishi.

Transformatsiya fazasi – 1 haftaning oxirgi-2 haftaning boshidan kuzatiladi. Bifidobakteriyalar ko'payib asosiy ichak mikroflorasi deb hisoblana boshlaydi.

Issiqlik almashinuvining tranzitor buzilishi

Tranzitor gipotermiya - bola tug'ilgandan so'ng dastlabki 30 daqiqa davomida teri va to'g'ri ichak harorati pasayadi, oradan bir soat o'gach, badan harorati mo'tadillashadi. Agar tug'ruq xonasidagi harorat 22-23 bo'lsa, bolaning harorati 35,5-35,7°S-gacha tushishi mumkin. Harorat qo'l va oyoqlarda yanada pastroq bo'ladi.

Tranzitor gipertermiya deb bola hayotining dastlabki 3-5 kunlarida xona haroratining yuqori bo'lishi (38,5-39,5°S), bolani nihoyatda o'rab-chirmash natijasida kuzatiladi, hamda bolaga yetarli miqdorda ona suti bilan emizmaslik,

isitish vositalari yonida yotishi natijasida modda almashinuvining buzilishi oqibatida tana haroratining ko'tarilishiga aytiladi. Chaqaloqlarda issiqlik almashinuvining tranzitor buzilishi sabablari bartaraf etilsa, bu holatlar yengilgina o'tib ketadi.

Buyrak faoliyatining tranzitor o'zgarishlari

Erta neonatal oliguriya - barcha sog'lom chaqaloqlar hayotining dastlabki 3 kunida kuzatilib, bu holat organizmga nisbatan kam suyuqlik tushayotgani va qon aylanishining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari bilan bog'liqdir. Ajralayotgan siydik miqdori birinchi kunda taxminan soatiga 0,75 - 1ml/kg, keyinchalik soatiga 2-5 ml/kg ni tashkil etadi. Bu holat yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni kompensator - moslashuv reaksiyasi bo'lib hisoblanadi.

Fiziologik proteinuriya (albuminuriya) - barcha chaqaloqlarda hayotining dastlabki kunlarida kuzatiladi. Bu holat koptokchalar va naychalar o'tkazuvchanligining oshganligi bilan bog'liq.

Buyrakning siydik kislotasi infarkti, bola hayotining dastlabki haftasi oxirida paydo bo'ladi. Bunda siydik kislotasi kristallar shaklida buyrakning yig'uvchi kanalchalari bo'shlig'iga to'planadi, natijada siydik rangi o'zgaradi, loyqalanadi va bolani o'ragan yo'rgakda sarg'ish-g'isht rangli dog' qoladi. Bu holat maxsus davolashni talab etmaydi, ammo bolaning etarli darajada ona suti bilan ta'minlanishiga e'tibor berish lozim.

Jinsiy krizlar

Jinsiy krizlar 65-70% chaqaloqlarda kuzatiladi.

Fiziologik mastopatiya - sut bezlarining kattalashishi tug'ilgandan so'nggi 3-4 kunlarda paydo bo'lib, bola hayotining 7-8 kunlarida eng katta hajmga etadi, so'ngra asta-sekin kichiklashib, neonatal davrning oxiriga kelib, asli holiga qaytadi.

Ko`pchilik hollarda bunday kattalashgan bezni bosib ko`rilganda, sutga o`xshash suyuqlik chiqadi.

Metroragiya. Qiz chaqaloqlar hayotining 5-7 kunlarida ba`zan (5-10% xollarda) 1-2 kun davomida kam-kamdan (0,5-1,0 ml) tashki tanosil a`zolaridan qon ajralishi kuzatiladi.

Toshma (miliya) teri yuzasidan ozgina ko`tarilib turadi va asosan burun parragi, peshona va engakda, ayrim hollarda esa butun badan terisida joylashgan bo`ladi

Chaqaloqlar fiziologik sariqligi

Chaqaloqlar fiziologik sariqligining sababi qonda bevosita bilirubin miqdorining oshib ketishi barcha chaqaloqlarda hayotining dastlabki 2-3 kunlarida kuzatilib, 60-70% hollarda u ko`zga yaqqol tashlanadigan sariqliqqa olib keladi

Bunda teri va shilliq pardalarning sarg`ayishi bola hayotining 2-3 kunlarida yuzaga kelib, bog`lanmagan (konyugatsiyalanmagan) bilirubinning miqdori muddatida tug`ilgan bolalarda 51-60 mkmol`/l, muddatiga yetmay tug`ilgan bolalarda esa 85-103 mkmol`/l gacha ko`payadi

Bilirubinni qondagi maksimal miqdori 130-170 mkmol`/l ni tashkil etadi.

Tana vaznining o`tkinchi (tranzitor) kamayishi

Tana vaznining tranzitor kamayishi bola hayotining 3-4 kunlarida sodir bo`lib, u 8%-dan 10%-gacha buladi. Odatda vaznining bunday kamayishi 6%-dan oshmaydi. Muddatiga yetmay tug`ilgan bolalarda tana vaznining fiziologik kamayishi 12-14%-ni tashkil etadi.

Tana vaznining fiziologik kamayishi 3 darajaga ajratiladi:

1 - daraja - tana vaznining 6%-dan kam miqdorda kamayishida suvsizlanish (eksikoz)ning belgilari kuzatilmaydi, lekin bolaning ochko`zlik bilan emishini sezish mumkin

2 daraja - tana vazni 6-10%-gacha kamayishi bilan kechadi. belgilari: shilliq pardalarning qizarishi, teri burmalar qayta tiklanishining buzilishi, bolaning bir xil tovush bilan yig'lashi, yurak urishi va nafas olishining tezlashishi kuzatiladi

3 daraja - tana vazni 10%-dan ziyodga kamayishi bilan kechib, bunda chanqash alomatlari: teri va shilliq pardalarning quruqligi, katta liqildoqning botishi, bezovtalanish, kuchli taxikardiya, qo`l va oyoqlarning sovub qolganligi xosdir.

Teridagi o`tkinchi holatlar

Oddiy eritema deb bola tug'ilgandan so`nggi 2 kunda tana terisining qizarishiga aytiladi. Odatda bu xol bola hayoti dastlabki haftasining oxiriga borib yuqoladi. Fiziologik eritema muddatiga etmay tug'ilgan bolalarda va onasi kandli diabet bilan og'rigan bolalarda nisbatan uzoqroq (2-3 haftagacha) saqlanib turadi.

Terining fiziologik qipiqlanishi bola hayotining 3-5-chi kunlarida paydo bo`lib, asosan ko`krak kafasi va qorin sohasida kuzatiladi. Bola vaqtdan o`tib tug'ilsa, bu holat kuchliroq bo`lishi mumkin.

Tug'ruk shishi - chaqaloq gavdasining qaysi qismi bilan tug'ilgan bo`lsa, shu joyda, qisilish oqibatida vena qon tomirlarida qon turib qolishidan kelib chiqadi.

Toksik eritema – allergoid reaksiya terida qizil dog'lar sifatida namoyon bo`lib, ba`zan uning markazida tuguncha yoki pufakchalar ham bo`lishi mumkin. Bu holat 20-25% chaqaloqlarda uchrab, bola hayotining 2-5 kunlarida paydo buladi. Bu dog'lar ko`pincha bug'imlar atrofi, dumba sohasi, ko`krak qafasining oldi tomonida joylashadi

Foydalanilga adabiyotlar:

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<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

Internet resurslar:

<https://uz.wikipedia.org/>

<https://www.ziyouz.com/>

<https://ttatf.uz/bolalar-kasalliklari-propedevtikasi-bolalar-kasalliklari-va-uash-pediateriya-kafedrasi/>

https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bolalar_kasalliklari

Iqlim o'zgarishlari

ILhomova Durdona Shavkatovna

Qashqadaryo viloyati nishon tumani 33 – umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqola iqlim o'zgarishlari haqida bo'lib, unda iqlimning injiqliklari, tabiatdagi o'zgarishlar, insoniyatga qay darajada ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkinligi, issiq va o'ta sovuq iqlim sharoyitlari haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Iqlim, issiq, sovuq, global, toshqin, sabab, ekalogiya, tadqiqot.

Аннотация: Эта статья об изменении климата, в которой обсуждаются капризы климата, изменения в природе, степень, в которой они могут повлиять на человечество, а также жаркие и очень холодные климатические условия.

Ключевые слова: климат, жаркий, холодный, глобальный, наводнение, причина, экология, исследование.

Abstract: This article is about climate change, which discusses the vagaries of climate, changes in nature, the extent to which they can affect humanity, and hot and very cold climates.

Key words: climate, hot, cold, global, flood, cause, ecology, research.

Sayyoramizdagi havoning global isishi oqibatida keying o'n yillikda 250 ming odam yashash joyini tashlab ketishga majbur bo'ldi. Global isishdan va ekologik

halokatlardaneng avvalo bolalar azyat chekmoqda. Hattoki rivojlangan mamlakatlarda ham globalisishdan aholining eng muhtoj va zaif qatlami zarar ko'radi. Bu haqida Bryusselda bo'lib o'tgan ekologik konferensiyada ham ma'lum qilindi.

Tadqiqotlar natijalariga ko'ra, ushbu yuz yillik so'ngida suv bilan ta'minlovchi Alp muzliklarining 75%i va Tibet cho'qqilari eriydi. Tinch okeanidagi riflar, yo'lbarslar, katta toshbaqalar, Amazonka, Ganga oqib o'tadigan Sundarbans milliy bog'idagi mango o'rmonlari, Maldiv orollari tillog'ochlari—bularning barchasi suv ostida qoladi deb taxmin qilinmoqda. Lekin BMT mutaxassislarinig fikricha, bir qancha mamlakatlarda iqlim yaxshilanadi. Bular Rossiya, Kanada va Skandinaviya mamlakatlaridir. Gap bir qator o'zgarishlar haqida aynan qishloq xo'jaligida ishlab chiqarish keskin ko'tarishi bo'yicha ketmoqda. Bu xulosalarga qarshi chiqish qiyin, chunki xulosalar 29 mingdan ortiq ilmiy axborotlar tekshirilgandan so'ng bayon qilingan. Bu axborotlarning 2/3 qismi esa sayyoramiz tobora isib borayotganligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Hukumatlararo ekspertlar guruhi Yer ilgari hisob-kitob qilinganidan ko'ra tezroq isib borayotganini ma'lum qilishmoqda. Dunyo bo'yicha o'rtacha harorat 1,1 darajaga ko'tarilgan. Bu esa 2040 yilga borib o'rtacha harorat 1,5 darajaga oshishini bildiradi.

Issiq to'lqinlar, kuchli shamollar, qurg'oqchilik, suv toshqinlari va yong'inlar yanada ko'proq sodir bo'la boshladi, muzliklar erishi yanada kuchaydi. Ayniqsa, joriy yilda bu jarayon judayam tezlashganini kuzatishimiz mumkin.

O'rmon yong'inlari

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Fransiya janubi, Ispaniya va Italiyaning Sardiniya orolida keng miqyosdagi oʻrmon yongʻinlari natijasida minglab gektar maydonlardagi oʻrmon va qishloq xoʻjalik yerlariga ziyon yetdi.

13 iyul kuni Kaliforniya shimolida boshlangan va Diksi nomini olgan keng koʻlamli yongʻinlar natijasida 200 ming gektardan ziyod maydonlar zararlandi.

Shimoliy Makedoniya hukumati yirik oʻrmon yongʻinlari sababli bir oyga inqirozli vaziyat rejimini joriy etdi.

Anomal issiq tufayli Turkiya gʻarbi va janubida ham dahshatli yongʻinlar yuz berishi natijasida sayyohlik tadbirlari, ekskursiyalar butunlay toʻxtatildi. Qishloq xoʻjalik maydonlari, fermalar yongʻin ichida qolib, chorva mollari nobud boʻldi.

Gretsiyada ham bir necha kundan buyon kuchli oʻrmon yongʻinlari davom etmoqda. Ofat bir haftadan ortiq vaqt mobaynida havo harorati 40 darajadan yuqori boʻlishi oqibatida sodir boʻlgan. Ayrim hududlarda havo harorati 47 darajagacha koʻtarilgan.

Rossiya sharqidagi Yoqutiston Respublikasida oʻrmon yongʻinlari, rasmiy ma'lumotlarga koʻra, 6 mln gektar hududni qamrab olgan — bu Belgiya hududidan ikki barobar katta.

Jazoirdagi kuchli yongʻinlar oqibatida halok boʻlganlar uchun mamlakatda 3 kunlik motam eʼlon qilindi.

Suv toshqinlari

Tabiiy ofatlarning yana bir dahshatlisi suv toshqinlaridir. Afgʻoniston sharqida joylashgan Nuriston viloyatida yuz bergan toshqinlarda kamida 150 kishi halok boʻldi.

Xitoyning Jyengjou shahrida kuchli yomgʻir yogʻishi natijasida suv toshqinlari sodir boʻldi va bir qancha insonlarning hayotiga nuqta qoʻyildi.

Hindistonning Goa va Maharashtra shtatlarida ro'y bergan keng ko'lamli suv toshqinlaridan keyin minglab binolar vayron bo'ldi.

Belgiyada 14–16 iyul kunlari yuz bergan toshqinlar 10 mlrd yevrodan ko'proq zarar yetkazgan.

G'arbiy Germaniyada minglab odamlar suv toshqinlari sabab uylarini tark etdi, 100 mingdan ortiq kishi elektr ta'minotisiz qoldi.

Anomal issiq

3–7 iyun kunlari Toshkentda uch asrning maksimum harorati kuzatilgani qayd etilgandi. Poytaxtda 5, 7 va 8 iyul kunlari yana rekord darajadagi issiq harorat takrorlandi.

Fransiyaning ijtimoiy masalalar va sog'liqni saqlash vaziri Anes Byuzen yozda kuzatilgan anomal issiqlik 1,5 ming kishining o'limiga sabab bo'lganini ma'lum qildi.

Kanadaning Britan Kolumbiyasi provinsiyasida anomal issiq havo sababli deyarli 500 kishi vafot etgan. Provinsiyada havo harorati rekord ko'rsatkich — 49,6 darajaga yetgan. Bungacha Kanadada harorat 45 darajadan oshmagan.

Yaponiyada sakkiz mingdan ortiq odam kasalxonalarga yotqizilgan. Bunga jazirama tufayli issiqlik urishi sabab sifatida ko'rsatilgan.

Bu hodisalarning har biridan iqlim o'zgarishi insoniyatga qanchalik xavf tug'dira boshlaganini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Mutaxassislar asrlar davomida dengiz sathining ko'tarilishini bashorat qilmoqdalar, ilgari «asr toshqini» deb hisoblangan narsa 80 yil ichida har yili sodir bo'ladigan hodisaga aylanishi mumkin.

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«Cloud to Street» kompaniyasi mutaxassislari tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, XXI asr boshidan buyon suv toshqinidan jabr ko'rgan odamlar soni 24 foizga ortgan. Bu ko'rsatkich olimlarning prognozidan 10 barobar ko'p.

Olimlarning hisob-kitobicha, 2000 yildan 2018 yilgacha toshqinlar sayyoramizning 2,23 mln kvadrat kilometrlik hududiga zarar keltirgan, toshqinlardan 290 millionga yaqin kishi jabr ko'rgan.

Suv toshqinlarining qariyb 90 foizi Janubiy va Janubi-Sharqiy Osiyo mamlakatlariga, ayniqsa Hind, Ganga-Braxmaputra va Mekong daryolari mintaqasiga to'g'ri kelmoqda.

Bundan tashqari, sun'iy yo'ldosh ma'lumotlari Lotin Amerikasining janubiy qismi, Yaqin Sharq va Afrika mamlakatlarida ham suv toshqinlari ko'payganini ko'rsatadi.

Iqlim va demografik o'zgarishlar tufayli 2030 yilga borib suv toshqinlari yana 25ta mamlakatda yuz bera boshlashi prognoz qilinmoqda.

Greenpeace Australia Pacific tadqiqotlar bo'limi boshlig'i Nikola Kazulening ta'kidlashicha, global isish oqibatida Tinch okeanidagi ayrim orol davlatlar yo'q bo'lib ketishi mumkin. «Dunyo okeani sathining ko'tarilishi

Kiribati, Vanuatu va Sulaymon orollarini yashash uchun yaroqsiz holga keltiradi», deydi mutaxassis.

Ma'lumot berilishicha, 1900 yildan buyon dunyo okeani sathi 20 santimetrga ko'tarilgan.

Iqlim o'zgarishining asosiy sababi nimada?

Mutaxassislar iqlim o'zgarishining asosiy omili issiqxona effekti ekanligini ta'kidlashadi. Quyoshdan kelgan issiqlikning Yer sathida jamlanib, dimlanib qolishi issiqxona effekti deyiladi. Ya'ni quyoshdan kelgan nurni Yer ham o'z navbatida

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atmosfera orqali koinotga qaytaradi. Ushbu nurlarning bir qismi koinotga chiqib ketish o'rniga odamlardan chiqarilgan turli gazlarga yutiladi. Uning koinotga qaytib chiqib ketmasligi oqibatida Yer yuzi me'yoridan ortiq qiziydi va iqlimga ta'sir ko'rsatadigan issiqxona qatlami hosil bo'ladi.

Natijada sutka mobaynida eng yuqori va eng past harorat orasida kam farq bo'ladi. Ya'ni odamlar va tabiat tunda ham kunduzgi kabi issiq va dim havo ta'sirida qoladi.

Bunday sutkalik issiqlik esa keskin isish hodisasini keltirib chiqaradi.

Issiqxona effektini hosil qiluvchi asosiy gaz bu – karbonat angidrid. U atmosferaga ham tabiiy, ham sun'iy yo'l bilan qo'shiladi. Metan, azot oksidi kabi boshqa iflos gazlar havoga inson omili tufayli chiqarilib, bular bir butun issiqxona effekti darajasini belgilaydi.

Issiqxona effektini hosil qiluvchi gaz konsentratsiyalarining ortishi, sayyorada tabiiy issiqlik balansini buzadi va antropogen issiqxona effektini keltirib chiqaradi.

Hisob-kitoblarga ko'ra, 2100 yilga borib issiqxona effekti oqibatida global yalpi ichki mahsulot 20 foizdan ortiqqa pasayishi mumkin.

Shuningdek, hozirgi kunda asosiy muammolar sifatida antropogen omillar ta'siri va qurg'oqchilik natijasida uglerod gazini yutuvchi o'rmon maydonlari keskin qisqarib ketishi, ozon qatlamining yemirilishi, yovvoyi tabiat maydonlarining qisqarib borayotganini ham keltirib o'tish mumkin.

Iqlim o'zgarishi O'zbekistonda ham qator salbiy oqibatlarga olib kelyapti:

- Harorat ko'tarilishi natijasida suvning bug'lanish koeffitsiyenti oshishi hududlarda suv resurslari kamayishiga, tanqisligiga ta'sir etmoqda;
- Ekologik tanglik oqibatida yil davomida umuman yog'ingarchilik bo'lmagan kunlar soni ko'paymoqda;

- Tuproqning namligi kamayishi hisobiga takroriy qurg'ochilik xavfi ortmoqda va hosildorlik ko'rsatkichlari tushib ketmoqda;
- Orol dengiziga quyiladigan suv hajmining kamayishi daryo deltasining cho'lga aylanishi va qurigan dengiz tubida yangi cho'l maydonlari paydo bo'lishini tezlashtiryapti;
- Atmosfera havosida katta maydonlarda changlanish ortmoqda;
- Isish va sovish kabi anomal hodisalarning o'zgarishi qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari va mevalarning nobud bo'lishiga olib kelmoqda.

Mutaxassislar iqlim o'zgarishining oldini olish uchun bir qancha tavsiyalar berishgan:

- qazib olinadigan yoqilg'idan foydalanishni kamaytirish va qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalariga o'tish;
- energiya samaradorligini oshirish va sohalarni energiya tejoychi texnologiyalar bilan modernizatsiya qilish;
- tabiatda yashillikni ko'paytirish, o'rmon yong'inlarining oldini olish, daraxtzorlarni ko'paytirish;
- ekologik toza qishloq xo'jaligiga o'tish;
- tuproq tarkibidagi organik moddalarni saqlab qolish (chunki ularning yo'qolishi to'g'ridan to'g'ri issiqxona effektiga ta'sir qiladi);
- ekologik tejamkor transport turlariga o'tish.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

Internet resurslar:

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<http://innoconferences.iblogger.org/>

1. <https://uz.dualjuridik.org/>
2. <https://fvv.uz/uz/>
3. <http://geografiya.for.uz/>
4. <https://uzhurriyat.uz/>